

INTERPRETATION OF THE CONCEPT OF BEING IN THE VIEWS OF BERUNI AND IBN SINA

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Abstract: This article cites a brief overview of the scientific and philosophical legacy of Berunius and Ibn Sina, who played an important role in the development of philosophical thought of the early Renaissance, as well as the importance of correspondence between them, which is considered one of the most important scientific philosophical legacies, the opinions of our great allomas on teachings created by one of the ancient Greek philosophers

Keywords: The correspondence of berunius and Ibn Sina, the arithmetic of Xind, Euclid and Ptolemy, the isphahan Observatory, the atom, "on the sky", "physics", the atomistic doctrine, "Sam'al-kiyon"

Not only are the scientific and philosophical correspondence of thinkers Abu Raykhan Beruniy and Abu Ali ibn Sina, who have made a huge contribution to the development of World Science, and the merits of our other great thinkers, the scope of their scientific work and works, but also the fact that they laid the foundation for scientific schools that left a deep mark on the history of mankind. From this, it is important to pay special attention to the dialogues and correspondence between Abu Rayhan Beruniy and Abu Ali ibn Sino. The rich heritage of our great ancestors after our country gained its independence beruniy and Ibn Sina's scientific and philosophical correspondence was as much as the sources record, but until Beruniy's 18 questions about Aristotle's "on Heaven" and "physics", and Ibn Sina's answers to them were first published in Uzbek and Russian in Tashkent in the 50-70s of the last century, Shark scientist one of the translators of questions and answers prof. Yu.N.Zavadovsky says that "The idea that Ibn Sina, who was widely abandoned in scientific research, was primarily a philosopher, is not just an outdated idea, but a cynical one". The ancient civilization and the existence of Aristotle, one of its major Representatives, whose views on the boyuk allomas of the Uyghur period, which grew up in Central Asia, the scientific and philosophical teachings of Ibn Sina and the Berunians serve as a connecting bridge of eastern and Western Tamaddun. The hilma-hilarity of the scientific research of berunius and Ibn Sina, their universality, is a unique phenomenon. Some of the scientific philosophical issues discussed in the correspondence of Ayonki Beruniy and Ibn Sina are also analyzed in their major fundamental works. In other words, in the Sox of Exact

Sciences, they introduced a lot of innovations to the fields of science to the concepts that exist in the Greeks, enriching these directions. Ibn Sina, for example, mastered the arithmetic of xind, mathematical concepts in the works of the Greek scientists Euclid and Ptolemy, shone with regular astronomical practice in Isfahan, and built an observatory in Isfahan, which he led in 1024-1032, made observations, and also wrote several treatises in bosokha. Berunius had also raised fan's theories about being, in particular, on fundamental issues . For example, Aristotle's meditations on the Fourth of the eight questions concerning "physics" can be evidence of our views cited above. Question: Why is a certain quarter of the Earth suitable for Prosperity, and another quarter, that is, one North and two South quarters, is not suitable, the conditions of these quarters are like the conditions of that prosperous Northern Quarter? The answer (Ibn Sina) is that the reasons that prevent the lands from prosperity are either the hardness of the heat or the hardness of the cold. But the reason for the stiffness of the heat is the restoration of the sun's rays or the constant presence of the sun's face in those places. For example, such a case would be at the South Pole. The reason for the severe cold is the fact that the sun Shu'la is lying on the ground. In such places, The Sun is more invisible. In my understanding, this is what is relevant to this issue. But the amount of worthless – unstable land depends on the amount of heat and coldness that generates noobodony, which is the matter of the owners of mathematical science. If you did not have the skill in this chapter of science, I would diligently enter into the mention of a part of the science of geometry – the mention of what causes ruin . The above points indicate that in correspondence, mainly concerning the macro-and micro-universe of ontological views, both thinkers describe their concepts. If in the matter of the infinity of space and time, which are considered habitable forms of matter, they are unanimous, then their philosophical approach to atoms, that is, invisible particles, has some peculiarities.

Now let's talk about the issue of the fact that in direct correspondence thinkers based their views on atoms on different approaches. In the universe, the cordinants of all particles and the strength of their interaction are considered important among scientists the question of the different interpretation of superconductors. Part of the scientific philosophical correspondence of berunius and Ibn Sina is also focused precisely on ushbumasala. In his fourth question, berunius singled out that it was in his views on atoms that Ibn Sina wanted to know his opinion The fact that bodies are in different forms and that they interact with each other, influence, and are in constant motion is not only at the

macro-Mega level, but also how they live in the macro universe is one of the main themes of Berunius and Ibn Sino Bach. In the ontological doctrine of Arestotel, Democritus also treats the Karash of atoms in Haki. He considers the concept of Indivisible particles to be a concept with a relative character. That is why Berunius does not add his fourth question to the words of those who say that Aristotle has indivisible particles (i.e. atoms)"? gives in shape. It should be noted that Berunius, in his question to Ibn Sina, made his position clearly short, stating the idea that people who say that there is an indivisible fragment will have more objections than this". From a philosophical point of view, Ibn Sina's attitude to the solution of this issue by Beruniy is interesting and remarkable from a scientific point of view.

Ibn Sina, in an in-depth study of the works of Aristotle, describes this issue in his treatise "Sam'al-kiyon", Article 6, on the basis of strong evidence, and describes what kind of body the Indivisible fragment is of Ibn Sina. Any indivisible piece (i.e. in the sense of a particle) says that it is something that has no two sides. Aristotle's views are defended and developed by Ibn Sina. The meaning of the word Arestotel that any piece is divided into something Infinite does not mean that it is divided forever in reality-Eanism is clarified by Ibn Sina. As long as each body is in the middle, that is, the core and its two sides. In his responses, Ibn Sina stated that" so that some fragments may be divided between these parties"and that some bodies are practically not divided from the very small". Ibn Sina recounted Beruni's question and his opinion, which he found its confirmation in the current atomistic doctrine. Small particles, that is, are cut into the smallest pieces and constantly move.

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Ibn Sina recounted Beruni's question and his opinion, which he found its confirmation in the current atomistic doctrine. Small particles, that is, are cut into the smallest pieces and constantly move. It is known that all elements that

are the composition of the atom (elements are constant movement and "if I were not limited to excessive stretching speech. I used to mention this," says Ibn Sina at the conclusion of his answers . Their scientific and philosophical discussions, especially in questions and answers that are known and popular in the history of science, are still waiting for their solution to the discussion. Berunius and Ibn Sina are considered encyclopedist scientists and great thinkers who created the East in the early Renaissance, adding a huge mass to the development of scientific and philosophical thought. The views of these two thinkers about the universe, which were thrown between them in the process of scientific observations, serve as one of the scientific and philosophical foundations of our national ideology and spiritual values.

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